

A tool to maximize air quality co-benefits while planning local climate actions: application to the Covenant of Mayors initiative

Supplementary materials

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1. Mapping step: correspondence between CoM and GAINS

In the calculation of air pollutant emission factors, a mapping step was needed to link Covenant of Mayors (CoM) and GAINS data (including emissions and energy consumption). Tables 1 and 2 show the correspondence between sectors and energy sources/carriers, respectively.

Table 1. Mapping step: correspondence between the Covenant of Mayors (CoM) and GAINS sectors

CoM sector		GAINS sector(s)
ID	Description	
3	residential_buildings	Domestic sector (DOM), DOM Single house boilers (<50 kW) – manual (DOM_SHB_M), DOM Single house boilers (<50 kW) - automatic (DOM_SHB_A), DOM Cooking stoves (DOM_STOVE_C), DOM Heating stoves (DOM_STOVE_H), DOM Fireplaces (DOM_FPLACE), DOM Medium boilers (<50MW) - automatic (DOM_MB_A), DOM Medium boilers (<1MW) - manual (DOM_MB_M), DOM Three-stone stove (DOM_PIT), DOM Domestic use of solvents (other than paint) (DOM_OS)
9	municipal_fleet_other	Cars (TRA_RD_LD4C), Light duty vehicles (TRA_RD_LD4T)
10	public_transport_other	Buses (TRA_RD_HDB)
11	private_transport_other	Cars (TRA_RD_LD4C), Light duty vehicles (TRA_RD_LD4T)
12	transport_non_allocated	Cars (TRA_RD_LD4C), Light duty vehicles (TRA_RD_LD4T), Buses (TRA_RD_HDB)
30	municipal_fleet_road	Cars (TRA_RD_LD4C), Light duty vehicles (TRA_RD_LD4T)
32	public_transport_road	Buses (TRA_RD_HDB)
36	private_transport_road	Cars (TRA_RD_LD4C), Light duty vehicles (TRA_RD_LD4T)

Notes: CoM sectors use emission factors calculated with the sum of activity data (namely air pollutant emissions and energy consumption) for the listed GAINS sectors. GAINS sectors are available at

<https://gains.docs.iiasa.ac.at/help/glossary/sectors.html>

Table 2. Mapping step: correspondence between the Covenant of Mayors (CoM) and GAINS energy sources/carriers

CoM carrier		GAINS carrier
ID	Description	
1	electricity	Electricity (ELE)
3	natural_gas	Natural gas (GAS)
4	liquid_gas	Liquified petroleum gas (LPG)
5	heating_oil	HO* = Sum of Medium distillates (MD) and Heavy fuel oil (HF)
6	diesel	Medium distillates (MD)
7	gasoline	Gasoline (GSL)
8	lignite	Brown coal/lignite, grade 1 (BC1)
9	coal	Hard coal, grade 1 (HC1)
10	other_fossil_fuel	ALL_FF* = Sum of Medium distillates (MD), Gasoline (GSL), Natural gas (GAS), Brown coal/lignite, grade 1 (BC1), Hard coal, grade 1 (HC1), Liquified petroleum gas (LPG), Derived coal (DC), Heavy fuel oil (HF), Hard coal, grade 2 (HC2), Brown coal/lignite, grade 2 (BC2)
12	biofuel	BIOF* = Sum of Medium distillates (MD), Gasoline (GSL), Natural gas (GAS) for Transport; Sum of Biogas (BIO), Charcoal (CHCOA) for the Residential sector and pollutants PM _{2.5} and VOC.
13	other_biomass	OB* (for Residential sector only) = Sum of Biomass fuels (OS1) in case of pollutants NH ₃ , NO _x or SO ₂ ; Sum of Fuel wood direct (FWD) in case of PM _{2.5} or VOC.
14	solar_thermal	Solar thermal (STH)
15	geothermal	Geothermal (GTH)
22	biogas	Biogas (BIO)

Notes: Carriers marked with asterisk (*) are a sum of GAINS carriers. Energy carriers in the GAINS model available at <https://gains.iiasa.ac.at/gains/download/GAINS-tutorial.pdf>

2. Regions: country grouping

As described in the article, we have divided the countries into broadly homogeneous groups and computed averaged emission factors for each of the groups ('EU12', 'EU15', 'Western Balkans' and 'Other'). The grouping of countries is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Grouping of countries into four regions: Central and Eastern Europe (EU12), Western Europe (EU15), Western Balkans (WB) and Other (OTH). The groups take into account the inclusion in the EU and related adhesion to regulations on air pollution.

GAINS country codes	ISO country codes	Region/group
ALBA	al	WB
ARME	am	OTH
AUST	at	EU15
AZER	az	OTH
BELA	by	OTH
BELG	be	EU15
BOHE	ba	WB
BULG	bg	EU12
CROA	hr	EU12
CYPR	cy	EU12
CZRE	cz	EU12
DENM	dk	EU15
ESTO	ee	EU12
FINL	fi	EU15
FRAN	fr	EU15
GEOR	ge	OTH
GERM	de	EU15
GREE	gr	EU15
HUNG	hu	EU12
ICEL	is	EU15
IREL	ie	EU15
ITAL	it	EU15
LATV	lv	EU12
LITH	lt	EU12
LUXE	lu	EU15
MACE	mk	WB
MALT	mt	EU12
MOLD	md	OTH
MONT	me	WB
NETH	nl	EU15
NORW	no	EU15
POLA	pl	EU12
PORT	pt	EU15
ROMA	ro	EU12
RUSS	ru	OTH
SERB	rs	WB
SKRE	sk	EU12
SLOV	si	EU12
SPAI	es	EU15
SWED	se	EU15
SWIT	ch	EU15
TURK	tr	OTH
UKRA	ua	OTH
UNKI	uk	EU15

3. Example of the application of the tool

This section illustrates the application of the tool to a city's SECAP data, as filled in the excel file (AQtool_2026-calculator_city_example).

Given the energy saving targets set by the city in the CAP (Table 4), the tool shows the baseline and resulting (projected) energy mix for the two sectors and for the two pathways, as illustrated in Figure 1. The Baseline Energy mix assumes the fuel mix shares are constant, and reduces each fuel's consumption proportionally (i.e., keeping the baseline relative shares). The MinGHG Energy mix assumes that the city prioritises the reduction of "dirtier" fuels, in terms of GHG emissions. In both pathways, three energy sources/carriers remain unaffected through time, assuming there is not reduction of energy use for those: electricity, geothermal and solar thermal. In the case of the residential sector of the selected city, the MinGHG Energy mix resulted in the complete phasing out of heating oil, liquid gas and coal, while in the transport sector, the relative share of diesel was reduced from 76 to 41%.

Table 4. Excerpt of action overview for a selected city

Target year	Base year	Sector	Final energy use in baseline year (MWh/year)	Estimated energy savings (MWh/year)	Estimated GHG reduction (t CO ₂ /year or t CO ₂ -eq/year)
2030	2017	Residential buildings	1 633 310	877 965	193 235
2030	2017	Transport	694 126	415 201	104 482

The fuels rank (assigning priority), in terms of GHG emissions, is based on GHG EFs by energy source/carrier provided by the city. In the online tool, in case of missing information, Bastos et al. (Bastos et al., 2024) is used instead; while in the excel (offline) calculator, information must be filled by the user.

Figure 2 provides an illustrative example of the tool's results for air pollutant emission reductions in the selected city. It is worth noting:

- GHG emissions. In the CAP, cities estimate GHG emissions in the BEI for each sector-carrier combination, as well as GHG emission reductions achieved for the actions in a sector. The data is used "as is" (i.e., GHG emissions are not recalculated according to the energy mix pathway).
- Air pollutant emissions. Emission changes for each sector-carrier combination have been computed using the energy reduction estimates in the CAP and the pollutant emission factors of the target year.
- Co-benefits. The figure shows the estimated co-benefits, in terms of air pollutant emission changes in relation to GHG emission change by air pollutant, sector and pathway. In the graph, circles refer to the transport sector, while triangles to the residential sector. The different colours identify the five pollutants. Lastly, the shaded area identifies the area where pollutants emission decrease is higher in percentage than GHG emission decrease. To allow a flexible use of the tool's results, all data illustrated in the Figures is also provided in tables. Table 5 shows the air pollutant reductions per sector and pollutant, also presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Illustration of tool results for select city: Final energy use (in MWh) of the Residential (left) and Transport sectors (right) in base and target years, for the Baseline Energy mix (top) and MinGHG Energy mix (bottom).

Table 5. Emissions in baseline and target year (in kt) and emission reduction (in %) per air pollutant and sector in the selected city in the MinGHG Energy Mix pathway.

Sector	Air pollutant	Emissions in baseline year (kt)	Emissions in target year (kt)	Emission reduction (%)
Residential buildings	NH ₃	0.00607	0.00382	37
Residential buildings	PM _{2.5}	0.08547	0.03764	56
Residential buildings	NO _x	0.19262	0.06331	67
Residential buildings	SO ₂	0.06493	0.00723	89
Residential buildings	VOC	0.11900	0.05393	55
Transport	NH ₃	0.01035	0.00713	31
Transport	PM _{2.5}	0.01563	0.00118	92
Transport	NO _x	0.65892	0.05292	92
Transport	SO ₂	0.00108	0.00038	65
Transport	VOC	0.04912	0.02366	52

Figure 2. Co-benefits results for the selected city, GHG and five air pollutant emissions. Results for 2030 are expressed for both mix pathways – that is, Baseline emission mix and MinGHG emission – and for the Residential (RES) and Transport (TRA) sectors.